

IODOMETRY OVER SPECTROPHOTOMETRY IN THE QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION OF VITAMIN C IN FRUITS

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Abstract: Vitamin C is widely found in many fruits and vegetables. It is the primary water-soluble anti-oxidant which prevents free-radicals generation in the body and damage to tissues. This investigation aims to quantitatively determine the vitamin-C content of orange and pineapple, by iodometric analysis. Six oranges and two pineapples were purchased from a local fruit vendor in Ilaro town, Ogun State. The fruits were equally divided into two groups each, where one group was left for seven days to naturally rot after being cut-open and exposed to initiate and hasten rotting; to obtain diseased fruit samples but the other group was not, hence, taken as healthy fruit samples. The healthy fruits were surface-disinfected with ethanol. The indicator dichlorophenol indophenol was used to qualitatively test for ascorbic acid in the fruits. Distilled water served as a control. The amount of ascorbic acid in each sample was determined by iodometry. The test showed that vitamin C is present in all the samples but absent in the distilled water. The healthy oranges showed a greater value of 111.5mg/100ml as compared to 75.8mg/100ml of the rotten oranges, also, the healthy pineapple showed a greater value of 34.1mg/100ml as compared to 15.8mg/100ml of the rotten pineapple. It was discovered that the healthy fruits relatively contained more ascorbic acid than the diseased ones. It can be concluded that iodometry could be potentially utilized in the quantitative assay for ascorbic acid, though with standardization, in fruits as an alternative to spectrophotometry, especially in the absence of electricity.

INTRODUCTION

Vegetables and fruits are two important sources of food nutrients being considered as having high nutritive and dietetic properties. The ingestion of vegetables and fruits has witnessed a remarkable elevation in the previous few

years by more than 30% (Barth, Hankison, Zhuang and Breidt, 2009). *Citrus sinensis*, also known as sweet orange, is the most popular of the citrus fruits. Just one orange provides 16% of the daily requirement for vitamin C. The consumption of pineapple (*Ananas comosus*)

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has been on the increase in Nigeria. Ascorbic acid is widely found in many fruits and vegetables. Ascorbic acid is a water-soluble anti-oxidant known to be important to health and for proper functioning of the human body. Ascorbic acid is vital for the growth and maintenance of healthy bones, teeth, gums, ligaments and blood vessels (Njoku, Ayuk and Okoye, 2011). Vitamin C is the primary water-soluble anti-oxidant, which prevents free-radicals generation in the body and damage to the tissues in the aqueous environment both inside and outside cells (Milind and Diev, 2012). The importance of fruits in human nutrition cannot be overestimated as they provide essential growth factors such as vitamins which are necessary for proper body metabolism (Al-Hindi, Al-Najada and Mohammed, 2011).

Most adults fail to meet-up with the recommended dietary allowance (RDA) of vitamin C per day (75mg - 90mg), especially from natural seasonal fruits even as they seemingly consume balanced diets, perhaps, due to the unavailability of adequate fruits, recent high cost due to post-harvest spoilage and other obstacles such as economic factors and even sheer ignorance of the importance of vitamin C in their diets. Vitamin C deficiency or low level in fruits could lead to scurvy, weakened immune system, bleeding of gums and other infections, as vitamin C is required for a healthy immune system. Iodometric technique for the quantitative determination of vitamin C is a relatively cheaper and more feasible alternative, as it is not dependent on electricity which is quite very epileptic and

erratic in most developing countries of the world including Nigeria, particularly in recent times, as compared with spectrophotometric technique.

This investigation aims to determine the ascorbic-acid content of two of the most commonly-consumed fruits (orange and pineapple) in Nigeria, by iodometric analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

This investigation was carried out at the Microbiology Laboratory of The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria. Six healthy oranges and two pineapples were purchased from a local fruit vendor in Ilaro town, Ogun State for the research. The fruits were equally divided into two groups each, where one group was left for seven days to naturally rot, after being cut-open and exposed to initiate and hasten rotting; to obtain diseased fruit samples but the other group was not, hence, taken as healthy fruit samples. Hand gloves were worn in the course of the investigation as a hygienic precautionary measure.

Disinfection

The healthy fruits were surface-disinfected with ethanol, to maintain their wholesomeness. 70% alcohol swab was used to disinfect the work surface to minimize contamination.

Qualitative Test for Ascorbic Acid

The indicator; dichlorophenol indophenol, otherwise called vitamin C reagent, was used to test for the presence of ascorbic acid in the oranges and pineapple (healthy and rotten). Distilled water, which served as a control, was used during this qualitative test for ascorbic

acid. Fifty drops of the vitamin C reagent were introduced into two test tubes each (Mashau and Mndalira, 2013). The juice of the fruit samples was squeezed-out and introduced in drops into the vitamin C reagent solution in each test tube for both the healthy and rotten groups accordingly. The drops were introduced until the solutions became clear from blue colouration i.e. this qualitatively shows the presence and level of ascorbic acid in the fruits. If the solution didn't become clear, that would indicate that there is very little or no vitamin C present. The fewer the drops required to make the solution colourless, the higher the vitamin C content.

Quantitative Assay for Ascorbic Acid by Iodometry

The amount of ascorbic acid in each sample was determined by iodometric titration; which is a redox reaction. In this method, iodine reacts with ascorbic acid to produce dehydroascorbic acid, which is a colourless product. To increase the solubility of the iodine used, it was improved by complexing the iodine with iodide to form triiodide. The iodine solution was prepared by dissolving 5g of potassium iodide in 5.35g of potassium iodate (KIO_3 ; 0.025M) in 200ml of distilled water. 30ml of 3M sulfuric acid was added. This was thereafter, dispensed into a 500ml measuring cylinder and diluted to a final volume of 500ml with distilled water. The solution was mixed and then transferred into a 600ml beaker and labeled as 'Iodine solution.' Each juice sample was sieved through a Muslin cloth to remove

pulp or seeds, for both the healthy and rotten orange and pineapple juice. 25ml of each juice sample was introduced into 125ml Erlenmeyer flask. The iodine solution was introduced into a burette and then titrated with each juice sample until an end-point was reached i.e. until a colour that persisted longer than 20 seconds was observed during swirling. This was done in duplicate and then recorded accordingly. Ten drops of 1% starch solution were added as indicator. This was prepared by adding 0.5g of soluble starch to 50ml near-boiling distilled water. This was mixed well and allowed to cool before use (Mashau and Mndalira, 2013). The initial and final iodine solution volumes were recorded after first rinsing the burette with a small volume of iodine solution and then filled afterwards.

RESULTS

The fruit samples (healthy and rotten) were qualitatively tested for the presence of vitamin C using the indicator; dichlorophenol indophenol, otherwise called vitamin C reagent. The test showed that vitamin C is present in all the samples, by the clarity of the solutions, after the vitamin C reagent was added to the samples. The solutions becoming clear confirmed the presence of vitamin C. The distilled water used as a control gave a negative result for the qualitative test for ascorbic acid, as there was no change nor clarity which implies that vitamin C is absent, after the distilled water was introduced in drops into the vitamin C reagent solution in a test tube, just as with the fruit juice samples.

Table 1: The Volumetric Analysis of the Healthy Orange Sample

	1st (Rough)	2nd	3rd
Final burette reading (cm³)	42.50	42.30	42.00
Initial burette reading (cm³)	0.00	0.00	0.00
Volume of iodine used	42.50	42.30	42.00

End-point observed = Purple colour persisted for more than 20secs.

Average titre value = 42.30 + 42.20 = 84.50

$84.50 \div 2 = 42.25\text{cm}^3$

This was taken to 0.1ml i.e. $42.25 \times 0.1 = 4.225\text{ml}$

The vitamin C concentration was calculated according to this formula;

Table 2: The Volumetric Analysis of the Rotten Orange Sample

	1st (Rough)	2nd	3rd
Final burette reading (cm³)	28.70	28.70	28.70
Initial burette reading (cm³)	0.00	28.70	28.70
Volume of Iodine used	27.70	28.70	28.70

End-point observed = Purple colour persisted for more than 20secs.

Average titre value = 28.70 + 28.70 = 57.40

$57.40 \div 2 = 28.70\text{cm}^3$

This was taken to 0.1ml i.e. $28.70 \times 0.1 = 2.870\text{ml}$

The vitamin C concentration was calculated according to this formula;

$\Delta\text{Vml (titrant)} \times 0.025\text{M (KIO}_3) \times 3\text{x MM of vit C} \times 100\text{ml} / 50\text{ml} = ? \text{ (mg/100ml)}$

$\Delta\text{Vml (titrant)} \times 0.025\text{M (KIO}_3) \times 3\text{x MM of vit C} \times 100\text{ml} / 50\text{ml} = ? \text{ (mg/100ml)}$

Taking that the chemical formula of vit. C is $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$, hence, the molar mass of vit. C is $(12 \times 6) + (1 \times 8) + (16 \times 6) = 176\text{g}$

Therefore,

$\text{Vit. C conc.} = 4.225 \times 0.025 \times 3 \times 176 \times 100 / 50 = 111.54\text{mg/100ml}$

Taking that the chemical formula of vit. C is $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$, hence, the molar mass of vit. C is $(12 \times 6) + (1 \times 8) + (16 \times 6) = 176\text{g}$

Therefore,

$\text{Vit. C conc.} = 2.870 \times 0.025 \times 3 \times 176 \times 100 / 50 = 75.8\text{mg/100ml}$

Table 3: The Volumetric Analysis of the Healthy Pineapple Sample

	1st (Rough)	2nd	3rd
Final burette reading (cm³)	14.50	27.30	13.00
Initial burette reading (cm³)	0.00	14.50	0.00
Volume of Iodine used	14.50	12.80	13.00

End-point observed = Purple colour persisted for more than 20secs.

Average titre value = 12.80 + 13.00 = 25.80

$25.80 \div 2 = 12.90\text{cm}^3$

This was taken to 0.1ml i.e. $12.90 \times 0.1 = 1.290\text{ml}$

The vitamin C concentration was calculated according to this formula;

$\Delta\text{Vml (titrant)} \times 0.025\text{M (KIO}_3) \times 3 \times \text{MM of vit C} \times 100\text{ml} / 50\text{ml} = ? \text{ (mg/100ml)}$

Taking that the chemical formula of vit. C is $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$, hence, the molar mass of vit. C is $(12 \times 6) + (1 \times 8) + (16 \times 6) = 176\text{g}$

Therefore,

$\text{Vit. C conc.} = 1.290 \times 0.025 \times 3 \times 176 \times 100 / 50 = 34.1\text{mg/100ml}$

Table 4: The Volumetric Analysis of the Rotten Pineapple Sample

	1st (Rough)	2nd	3rd
Final burette reading (cm³)	6.80	12.60	6.20
Initial burette reading (cm³)	0.00	6.80	0.00
Volume of Iodine used	6.80	5.80	6.20

End-point observed = Purple colour persisted for more than 20secs.

Average titre value = 5.80 + 6.20 = 12.0

$12.0 \div 2 = 6.0\text{cm}^3$

This was taken to 0.1ml i.e. $6.0 \times 0.1 = 0.60\text{ml}$

The vitamin C concentration was calculated according to this formula;

$\Delta\text{Vml (titrant)} \times 0.025\text{M (KIO}_3) \times 3 \times \text{MM of vit C} \times 100\text{ml} / 50\text{ml} = ? \text{ (mg/100ml)}$

Taking that the chemical formula of vit. C is $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$, hence, the molar mass of vit. C is $(12 \times 6) + (1 \times 8) + (16 \times 6) = 176\text{g}$

Therefore,

$\text{Vit. C conc.} = 0.60 \times 0.025 \times 3 \times 176 \times 100 / 50 = 15.8\text{mg/100ml}$

During the iodometric analysis of the healthy and rotten oranges for vitamin C concentration, the healthy oranges showed a greater value of 111.5mg/100ml as compared to 75.8mg/100ml of that of the rotten oranges. Also, the healthy pineapple too showed a greater value of 34.1mg/100ml as compared to 15.8mg/100ml of that of the rotten pineapple, as shown in tables 1 to 4. The quantity, in mg/100ml, of ascorbic acid in the healthy oranges was about one-quarter more than the one in the rotten ones while the quantity in mg/100ml of ascorbic acid in the healthy pineapple was about double more than the one in the rotten one.

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DISCUSSION

At the completion of the research, it was discovered that the healthy fruits relatively contained more ascorbic acid than the diseased (rotten) ones. The relative margin could be perceived to be as a result of the presence of the spoilage microorganisms in the rotten samples; utilizing some of the available ascorbic acid present in the orange and pineapple fruits for their growth and survival. During the iodometric analysis, it was observed that the rotten samples required lesser of the iodine solution to arrive at the end-point than the healthy samples, supposedly because of the lower vitamin C concentration in them. Dorby, Chaluz, Wilson and Nisneiweski (1989) somewhat reported a similar finding that fermentation by microorganisms on fruits often affect the symptoms expression and nutritional content of fruits, unlike chemical fermentation. Though, the iodometric technique has its limitations as it is quite laborious, time-consuming, prone to error and inaccuracy due to parallax and spillage but nevertheless, it is still a sure substitute in the absence of electricity, which is a major determining factor in using a spectrophotometric technique. Besides, a spectrophotometre requires a technical-know-how for its operation and it could be expensive too.

The similar research on the determination of ascorbic acid levels by iodometric method performed by Ashiagbor and Atta-Eyison (2024) but instead in three varieties of local Ghanaian oranges shows its potentiality as a valid and veritable alternative technique. The

researchers further determined different storage conditions on the oranges they sampled between two and six days.

Vitamin C or ascorbic acid is important for the human body. For instance, the vitamin C (ascorbic acid) content of pineapple is said to be 47.8mg/100ml. From a toxicological standpoint, vitamin C supplementation is relatively safe, even in mega dose levels. The current recommended dietary daily allowances for vitamin C are 90mg for men, 75mg for women and 120mg for breastfeeding women (UADA, 2013).

Fruits juiced must be stored at cool temperature; the vitamin C content does not reduce, however, storing fruit juice at high temperature results in loss of vitamin C content. This is because vitamin C is sensitive to high temperature and it can easily oxidize.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded, from this study, that iodometry could be potentially utilized in the quantitative assay for the ascorbic acid in fruits as an alternative to spectrophotometry, though with standardization. There was a drastic reduction in the vitamin C concentration of the rotten fruit samples as compared to the healthy ones. This clearly indicates that those microorganisms must have potentially utilized some of the available vitamin C in the rotten fruits for their metabolism while simultaneously causing deterioration in those fruits.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Fruits are important component of a healthy diet, supplying the much-needed vitamin C which the body can't synthesize on its own and

also required to fight infections as they contain anti-oxidants, hence;

❖ The iodometric method of determining the vitamin C content in fruits including orange and pineapple, with the aim of meeting-up with its daily requirement for healthy living, could be considered as a substitute based on its relative affordability and non-dependence on electricity, especially in developing nations.

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❖ Rotten fruits could be processed into ethyl alcohol (ethanol) by fermentation for industrial use.

❖ Further investigations should be carried-out by juxtaposing the results obtained against that of vitamin-C standard solution and the research should be standardized by spectrophotometry.

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